

Analysis of Sensory Impression Factor Structures of Jomon Potteries through a Semantic Differential Method Viewing 3D Models on MR equipment

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Abstract—As Jomon pottery, particularly flame-like pot, is increasingly perceived by museum visitors as a form of artistic expression rather than merely archaeological artifacts, it is of interest to study the sensory impressions associated with it, and to investigate commonalities with the spatial cognitions that modern people have of Jomon pottery. A sensory impression test was conducted using 3D models of pottery on Microsoft HoloLens with 73 participants, who rated 16 sensory adjectives through the Semantic Differential Method and also made free selections of impressive parts of the pottery. Factor analyses and analyses of variance were performed on these adjective groups, identifying factors such as "vigor," "attractiveness," "surface smoothness," and "lightness." The Okinohara and Umataka types consistently scored significantly higher on "vigor" (the first factor) and "attractiveness." The complete alignment of these two typological groups in sensory impressions and spatial cognitions suggests a shared commonality between them.

Keywords— sensory impression, Jomon potteries, Semantic Differential Method, factor analysis, analysis of variance, cognitive structures, spatial cognitions

I. INTRODUCTION

a Shinano River and the Jomon People

The Shinano River, sourced from Mount Kobushigatake on the borders of Nagano, Saitama, and Yamanashi Prefectures, flows through the Saku Basin, Ueda Basin, and Nagano Basin as the Chikuma River in Nagano Prefecture. Upon merging with the Sai River in Nagano City, originating from Mount Yarigatake, it assumes the name Shinano River and continues to flow into the Sea of Japan at the border of Niigata Prefecture. As Japan's longest river, it spans a total length of 367 kilometers. The Jomon people, who settled in these basins 13,000 years ago, began producing pottery. Numerous archaeological sites from this era are densely concentrated in the upper reaches of the Shinano River basin [1].

b Emergence of Flame-like Pots in a Snowy Environment

Approximately 8,000 years ago, a significant environmental change occurred with the advent of a warm

current flowing into the Sea of Japan, leading to increased snowfall. This snowy environment persisted, and around 5,000 years ago, during the middle Jomon period, flame-like pots emerged. Characterized by designs and forms that evoke vigorous flames, flowing water, and waves, this pottery style is remarkably expressive. A distinctive feature of middle Jomon period potteries in the Shinano River basin are the presence of protrusions, most notably exemplified by flame-like pots adorned with four particularly bold protrusions, which represent a hallmark of the era [1].

Flame-like pot appears to be perceived as a form of artistic expression rather than archaeological artifact by museum visitors. Therefore, studying the sensory impressions of participants regarding Jomon potteries, including flame-like pots, is of significant interest.

c Spatial Cognition of the Jomon People and Potteries

Archaeologist and anthropologist Kobayashi Tatsuo (1996) proposed spatial cognitive differences between the Jomon people and modern societies. He described houses as "rather holy container spaces," a concept perceived as such by the Jomon people [2].

Ishii (2010) further developed anthropological hypotheses on the spatial recognition of ancient Jomon people, defining cultural spaces during the Jomon period. He expanded upon Kobayashi Tatsuo's hypothesis, focusing on the "container nature" of space and analyzing the structure of spatial cognition and the symbolism of human-made spaces in the Jomon period, encompassing "houses," "villages," "monuments," and earthenware spaces [3].

Building on these hypotheses, Ishii suggested that Jomon potteries represent micro spaces reflecting the sensibilities and sensory impressions of the pottery makers.

d Commonalities of Cognitive Processes and Mind Structures

The work "Cognitive Archaeology, Body Cognition, and the Evolution of Visuospatial Perception" (2023) [4]

illustrated how body perception and spatial sensing might have evolved in humans, suggesting that both body perception and spatial sensing share commonalities among all human beings.

Matsumoto (2000) [5] employed the theory and methods of cognitive archaeology to argue that the mind and body have developed together over the course of human evolution. Therefore, the structure of the mind should be considered as universally common to the same extent as the structure of the human body. She also claimed that there is a certain degree of universality in human cognitive processes and cognitive structures, and that the same models and conceptual frameworks can be applied across cultural and social differences.

e Quantitative Approach of Sensory Impression Factor Structure, Semantic Differential Method

The Semantic Differential Method (SDM) is widely employed in psychology and the social sciences to examine participants' perceptions. This method assesses participants' attitudes and emotional responses toward specific concepts by utilizing bipolar adjective pairs (e.g., "beautiful–ugly," "strong–weak") on a 5- or 7-point rating scale. By capturing the connotative meaning of these concepts, the SDM offers a nuanced understanding of sensory impressions (Suzuki and Gyoba, 2003)[6].

Thus SDM can be defined as a psychophysical testing approach used to extract human sensory perceptions or psychological images through participants' evaluations on scales with bipolar adjective pairs. This method has been widely employed to measure human sensory responses to various stimuli, including visual, auditory, gustatory, and textural elements.

Kawabata and Nagashima (1986) utilized the SDM to evaluate the taste and texture of three types of wild rice[7].

The Semantic Differential data consists of three modes: "participants," "scales," and "concepts"[8]. Toyoda and Saito (2005) developed positioning analysis methods to analyze multi-group three-mode data, as well as four-mode data[8].

Dai (1982) employed three-mode factor analysis to assess sensory perceptions of industrial chair designs[9].

Yamaguchi et al. (2004) explored the relationship between psychophysical and semantic characteristics of shapes by providing participants with stimuli comprising 32 geometric diagrams. These diagrams varied in magnitude along parameters corresponding to four psychological dimensions: curvedness, regularity, complexity, and openness/closedness, referred to as psychophysical features. Using the SDM, these shapes were evaluated, and factor analysis identified three factors: mildness, stability, and activity[10].

Semantic Differential data, typically comprising more than 20 bipolar adjective pairs, is commonly analyzed using factor analysis, as this method reduces dimensionality by identifying patterns within the adjective pair scores[6].

Factor analysis clusters related adjectives into underlying "factors" (e.g., happiness, attractiveness), facilitating interpretation by summarizing the data into fewer, meaningful dimensions. This approach is widely applied to

Figure 1 Jomon pottery hologram processing

extract core dimensions in studies of attitudes and perceptions (Wada et.al. 2003)[11].

II. RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND OBJECTIVES

One of the research questions is whether cognitive structures and body perception can be measured using MR equipment, by employing verbal descriptors (adjective scales) and selections of impressive vessel parts. If these methods are unsuitable or insufficient for observing cognitive structures and body perception, what additional measures should be taken—such as recording participants' oral expressions of their impressions or using gaze tracking?

Another question is whether the perception and cognitive processes of modern people regarding Jomon earthenware of the target, dating approximately 5,000 years ago, are the same as those of the Jomon people.

The final question is whether, if we successfully extract parameters or data related to sensory impressions or cognitive processes using data science methods, it is possible to represent the cognitive structure through deep learning models.

This is an introductory study focusing on participants' sensory impression structures of ancient artifacts, particularly middle Jomon pottery, using MR equipment. The study aims to gather basic information about participants' perception and cognitive responses before conducting a comprehensive study, which will attempt to represent cognitive processes through deep learning models by applying large amounts of material data and human cognitive response data, such as gaze heatmaps, using MR equipment. The obtained data can be used for the deep learning model development.

III. METHODOLOGIES

a Hologram Preparations

Eight Jomon potteries from the Middle Jomon Period, including two flame-like pots and a Sue ware from the 6th century AD, were optically scanned using the Go! Scan Spark scanner made by Creaform at a resolution of 0.05 mm. The scanner is equipped with three shape-tracking cameras, one color camera, and one white light projector, which collectively generates mesh data containing color and texture

information via VXElements software. Subsequently, the mesh data with color and texture information was exported in the OBJ file format. These nine pottery files were then downsized and the color and texture maps were re-baked using Blender CG software for display on Microsoft HoloLens (Figure 1). The nine potteries are listed as follows:

Scree plots

Figure 2 Scree plots of Semantic Differential Method

Table 1 Potteries used for the experiment with typologies

No.	Sample ID	Typology
1	Okinohara-1	Okinohara, Coil Building
2	Okinohara-2	Okinohara, Coil Building
3	Umataka-flame1	Umataka (flame-like pot), Coil Building
4	Upper Ento	Upper Ento, Coil Building
5	Umataka-flame2	Umataka (flame-like pot), Coil Building
6	Umataka-crown1	Umataka (crown-like pot), Coil Building
7	Umataka-crown2	Umataka (crown-like pot), Coil Building
8	Katsusaka	Katsusaka, Coil Building
9	Sue ware	Sue II-2, Wheel Forming

b Sensory Impression Experiment and statistical analyses

The experiment was conducted on July 11 and 13, 2023, in an experimental laboratory at Niigata University of International and Information Studies. Three Microsoft HoloLens devices were used. Visibility, with special attention to color differences, was adjusted among those MR devices. Three parallel holographic exhibitions were set up, labeling 9 sample names in one line on the floor, and downloading hologram contents of potteries on top of those labels. Heights and sizes were adjusted manually. Thus, nine pottery items were arranged in three rows. Each HoloLens only displays holograms that have been downloaded.

The sensory impressions of the nine potteries were measured using the Semantic Differential Method. Sixteen adjectives were referenced and chosen from 20 adjectives in a study on sensory impressions of words and drawings (Suzuki and Gyoba, 2003)[6].

The 16 bipolar adjective pairs were as follows:

- Beautiful-Ugly
- Pleasant-Unpleasant
- Likable-Repugnant
- Light-Heavy

- Cheerful-Gloomy
- Lively-Quiet
- Dynamic-Static
- Flashy-Modest
- Intense-Calm
- Powerful-Feeble
- Strong-Weak
- Soft-Hard
- Smooth-Rough
- Blunt-Sharp
- Relaxed-Tense
- Delicate-Rugged

Five scale ranges from "very applicable" to "strongly not applicable," were set each adjective pairs, and 73 participants chose an applicable scale each adjective. The results were analyzed by HAD, a statistical macro script [12] using Factor Analysis with maximum likelihood extraction, Promax rotation (Power=4), and Kaiser normalization. Analysis of variance was then conducted on the mean factor scores of the nine pottery items to explain variations in impression factors.

On top of the SD method of sensory impression measurements by those verbal adjectives, a measurement of impressive partial selections was made. This asks the participants the most impressive parts of the objects from the following: the rim of the vessel, the body of the vessel, the bottom of the vessel, the upper part of the vessel, the lower part of the vessel, the whole vessel, the inside of the vessel, or no particular part being impressive. Frequencies of the choices of the above were calculated and compared.

IV. RESULTS

The Scree plots are graphical presentations of factor variance plotted against the number of factors, used to determine the optimal number of factors before conducting factor analysis. Figure 2 depicts the Scree plots of the Semantic Differential (SD) method using 16 sensory impression adjectives. The lines show a sudden decrease at three factors, followed by four factors, both with eigenvalues exceeding 1.0. Therefore, three factors and four factors were selected for the factor analysis.

a Factor Analysis with Three Factors

The results are presented in Table 2. Three factor groups were derived from the sixteen adjective pairs based on factor load values greater than 0.448, as shown in Table 2.

The first factor (referred to as "Factor1") was labeled "vigor," encompassing adjectives such as "dynamic/static," "lively/quiet," "flashy/modest," "intense/calm," "cheerful/gloomy," "powerful/feeble," and "strong/weak."

The second factor was termed "attractiveness," representing adjectives like "beautiful/ugly" and "likable/repugnant."

The third factor was named "surface smoothness," capturing adjectives such as "smooth/rough," "relaxed/tense," "soft/hard," "blunt/sharp," "delicate/rugged," and "light/heavy."

Table 2 Factor analysis with three factors

samples = 657 variables = 16 factors = 3

extraction method = maximum likelihood
 rotational method = promax rotation (Power = 4)
 Kaiser normalization = Y

factor patterns number of iterations = 6
 convergence criterion = 0.0002

	vigor	attractive ness	surface smoothness	Commonality
SD adjective pairs	Factor1	Factor2	Factor3	
dynamic/static	.932	-.133	.082	.744
lively/quiet	.924	-.120	.117	.726
flashy/modest	.879	.012	-.025	.794
intense/calm	.833	.006	-.094	.748
cheerful/gloomy	.645	.110	.205	.468
powerful/feeble	.600	.177	-.114	.529
strong/weak	.579	.165	-.150	.509
pleasant/unpleasant	-.060	.915	.052	.805
beautiful/ugly	.002	.841	.010	.710
likable/repugnant	.143	.739	.003	.660
smooth/rough	-.121	-.030	.777	.667
relaxed/tense	-.061	-.013	.713	.533
soft/hard	.226	-.009	.683	.435
blunt/sharp	-.036	-.040	.679	.473
deliate/rugged	-.100	.251	.494	.343
light/heavy	.137	.016	.448	.192
factor contributions	5.054	3.219	2.885	
fitness	Deviation =	0.829	CFI =	.923
	$\chi^2 =$	537.062	RMSEA =	.098
	DF =	75	AIC =	633.832
	p =	.000	BIC =	835.778

reliability coefficient * α and ω coefficients are calculated from items in bold (negative loads are reversed)

	Factor1	Factor2	Factor3
α coefficients	.918	.880	.792
ω coefficients	.926	.885	.809
factor scores	.937	.896	.835

Reliability coefficient when not reversed

	Factor1	Factor2	Factor3
α coefficients	.918	.880	.792
ω coefficients	.926	.885	.809

Inter-factor correlation

	Factor1	Factor2	Factor3
Factor1	1.000	.437	-.258
Factor2	.437	1.000	.089
Factor3	-.258	.089	1.000

Factor structure (correlation coefficients with factors)

SD adjective pairs	Factor1	Factor2	Factor3
dynamic/static	.853	.281	-.171
lively/quiet	.841	.294	-.132
flashy/modest	.891	.394	-.251
intense/calm	.860	.362	-.309
cheerful/gloomy	.640	.410	.048
powerful/feeble	.707	.430	-.253
strong/weak	.690	.405	-.285
pleasant/unpleasant	.326	.893	.149
beautiful/ugly	.367	.842	.084
likable/repugnant	.465	.802	.032
smooth/rough	-.335	-.014	.805
relaxed/tense	-.250	.024	.727
soft/hard	.045	.151	.624
blunt/sharp	-.229	.004	.685
deliate/rugged	-.118	.251	.542
light/heavy	.029	.116	.414

Table 3 Factor analysis with four factors

samples = 657 variables = 16 factors = 4

extraction method = maximum likelihood
 rotational method = promax rotation (Power = 4)
 Kaiser normalization = Y

factor patterns number of iterations = 5
 convergence criterion = 0.001

	vigor	attractive ness	surface smoothness	weight	
SD adjective pairs	Factor1	Factor2	Factor3	Factor4	Commonality
lively/quiet	.955	-.096	-.016	.190	.761
dynamic/static	.947	-.115	-.024	.125	.757
flashy/modest	.857	.018	-.060	-.021	.784
intense/calm	.804	-.014	-.059	-.148	.760
cheerful/gloomy	.678	.158	.034	.284	.528
powerful/feeble	.527	.105	.096	-.477	.715
pleasant/unpleasant	-.101	.934	.031	.019	.799
beautiful/ugly	-.039	.868	-.019	.024	.712
likable/repugnant	.111	.774	-.050	.058	.668
blunt/sharp	-.043	-.105	.785	-.110	.573
smooth/rough	-.111	-.048	.749	.100	.667
relaxed/tense	-.060	-.042	.722	.036	.556
soft/hard	.246	.011	.558	.238	.430
delicate/rugged	-.111	.248	.472	.059	.342
light/heavy	.221	.103	.167	.584	.399
strong/weak	.504	.086	.073	-.509	.715
factor contributions	5.060	3.371	2.738	1.929	
fitness	Deviation =	0.223	CFI =	.986	
	$\chi^2 =$	144.445	RMSEA =	.046	
	DF =	62	AIC =	262.417	
	p =	.000	BIC =	522.702	

reliability coefficient * α and ω coefficients are calculated from items in bold (negative loads are reversed)

	Factor1	Factor2	Factor3	Factor4
α coefficients	.912	.880	.809	.358
ω coefficients	.934	.886	.831	.623
factor scores	.936	.898	.834	.622

Reliability coefficient when not reversed

	Factor1	Factor2	Factor3	Factor4
α coefficients	.912	.880	.809	-.557
ω coefficients	.934	.886	.831	.414

Inter-factor correlation

	Factor1	Factor2	Factor3	Factor4
Factor1	1.000	.478	-.178	-.325
Factor2	.478	1.000	.139	-.172
Factor3	-.178	.139	1.000	.318
Factor4	-.325	-.172	.318	1.000

Factor structure (correlation coefficients with factors)

SD adjective pairs	Factor1	Factor2	Factor3	Factor4
lively/quiet	.850	.326	-.138	-.109
dynamic/static	.856	.313	-.168	-.170
flashy/modest	.883	.423	-.216	-.322
intense/calm	.856	.388	-.251	-.426
cheerful/gloomy	.655	.438	.026	.047
powerful/feeble	.715	.452	-.135	-.636
pleasant/unpleasant	.334	.887	.185	-.099
beautiful/ugly	.372	.843	.116	-.120
likable/repugnant	.471	.810	.056	-.127
blunt/sharp	-.197	.003	.743	.172
smooth/rough	-.300	-.014	.794	.383
relaxed/tense	-.220	.023	.739	.293
soft/hard	.074	.165	.592	.334
delicate/rugged	-.095	.251	.545	.203
light/heavy	.051	.131	.328	.547
strong/weak	.698	.425	-.167	-.665

Figure 3 Three Factor Score Variations in Potteries

Table 4 Three Factor Score Variations in Potteries

	1st factor	2nd factor	3rd factor	significance
Okinohara-1	3.820	4.146	2.831	**
Okinohara-2	3.587	3.986	3.016	**
Umataka-flame1	3.861	4.215	2.861	**
Upper Ento	2.407	3.425	3.660	**
Umataka-flame2	3.139	3.822	3.292	**
Umataka-crown1	3.605	3.845	2.925	**
Umataka-crown2	3.027	3.712	3.384	**
Katsusaka	2.507	3.516	3.708	**
Sue ware	2.127	3.502	4.011	**

Figure 4 Four Factor Score Variations in Potteries

Table 5 Four Factor Score Variations in Potteries

	1st factor	2nd factor	3rd factor	4th factor	significance
Okinohara-1	3.781	4.146	2.874	2.281	**
Okinohara-2	3.575	3.986	2.984	2.760	**
Umataka-flame1	3.838	4.215	2.784	2.623	**
Upper Ento	2.347	3.425	3.805	3.082	**
Umataka-flame2	3.153	3.822	3.186	3.384	**
Umataka-crown1	3.598	3.845	2.849	2.829	**
Umataka-crown2	3.050	3.712	3.244	3.596	**
Katsusaka	2.418	3.516	3.923	2.795	**
Sue ware	2.128	3.502	3.918	4.178	**

Table 6 Frequencies of impressed parts of vessels

	Okinohara -1	Okinohara -2	Umataka-flame 1	Upper Ento	Umataka-flame 2	Umataka-crown 1	Umataka-crown 2	Katsusaka	Sue ware
rim	36	29	34	7	31	30	31	18	10
upper part	41	35	40	6	30	34	28	17	4
lower part	3	10	7	14	6	11	10	9	3
bottom	3	5	3	3	4	4	2	2	5
whole vessel	4	6	9	35	9	13	11	32	36
inside vessel	7	7	11	8	5	4	6	6	12
not particular	1	2	2	13	7	4	10	6	15

b Factor Analysis with Four Factors

Table 3 presents the results of the four-factor analysis. The first factor was labeled "vigor," representing bipolar adjective pairs of "lively/quiet," "dynamic/static," "flashy/modest," "intense/calm," "cheerful/gloomy," and "powerful/feeble." The second factor was named "attractiveness," representing adjective pairs of "pleasant/unpleasant," "beautiful/ugly," and "likable/repugnant."

The third factor was termed "surface smoothness," encompassing bipolar adjective pairs of "blunt/sharp," "smooth/rough," "relaxed/tense," "soft/hard," and "delicate/rugged." The fourth factor was named "lightness," representing adjective pairs of "light/heavy" and "strong/weak (-6.65 correlation coefficient)."

c Analysis of Variance of Potteries on Three Factors

Table 4 presents the factor load scores of the potteries, and Figure 3 illustrates the variations among potteries across three factors.

In terms of typologies, all Okinohara types (Okinohara-1 and 2) and Umataka types (flame-1 and 2, crown-1 and 2) showed significantly higher scores for "vigor" (first factor) exceeding 3.0, and scores for "attractiveness" (second factor) exceeding 3.7.

On the other hand, Upper Ento, Katsusaka, and Sue ware exhibited significantly lower scores in the first factor. Figure 3 displays symmetric patterns between the first and third factors, "vigor" and "surface smoothness." Therefore, significantly higher scores were observed for Upper Ento, Katsusaka, and Sue ware in the third factor.

d Analysis of Variance of Potteries on Four Factors

Table 5 presents the factor load scores of the potteries, and Figure 4 illustrates the variations among potteries across four factors.

All Okinohara types (Okinohara 1 and 2) and Umataka types (flame1 and 2, crown1 and 2) exhibited significantly higher scores for "vigor" (first factor) exceeding 3.0 and scores for "attractiveness" (second factor) exceeding 3.7 (consistent with the results of the analysis of variance on three factors). The factor load scores of the third factor displayed symmetric patterns similar to those of the first factor (matching the results of the analysis of variance on three factors).

The factor load scores for the fourth factor, "lightness," exhibited a different pattern compared to that of the third factor. The second highest load score was observed in Umataka-crown2, followed by Sue ware, while significantly lower load values were found in Katsusaka.

Table 6 presents the frequency of pottery parts selected as impressive by the participants. Two distinct groups of pottery emerge based on the parts that were found to be impressive: the Okinohara and Umataka types were frequently noted for their impressive rims and upper parts, while the other three types were rated highly impressive across the entirety of the vessel.

V. DISCUSSIONS

a Sensory Impression Factor Structures

The results indicated that both the Okinohara and Umataka pottery types (including two flame-like pots) yielded significantly higher impression structures of "vigor" and "attractiveness" compared to other Jomon pottery (Upper Ento and Katsusaka) and Sue ware. Conversely, the significantly lower scores of these six pottery types on the third factor suggested stronger impressions of "roughness" as opposed to "surface smoothness." The scores of these nine potteries exhibited a symmetric pattern between the first factor, "vigor," and the third factor, "surface smoothness." This study provides initial evidence of the prominent sensory impression characteristics of the Okinohara and Umataka types, which are chronologically and geographically close. They exhibited significant sensory impressions of greater "vigor" and "attractiveness," along with higher "surface roughness."

b Correlation of Spatial Impressive Cognition and Sensory Impression Perceptions

The typologies of impressive pottery parts showed strong correlations with the sensory impression factor structures. All Okinohara and Umataka types, which were noted for their impressive rims and upper parts, exhibited higher scores in the impression factors of "vigor" and "attractiveness." In contrast, the other three types—Upper Ento, Katsusaka, and Sue ware—were perceived as less vigorous and attractive.

c Commonality between Spatial Cognition and Sensory Impressions

The observation that pottery groups with similar sensory impression factor structures and those where notable parts were similarly identified are identical suggests a strong commonality between human sensory impressions and spatial cognition. This finding implies that individuals tend to form sensory impressions based on the areas of an object they find interesting. These areas capture the observer's attention through distinctive features, such as the rims of flame-like pots, prominent protrusions, or three-dimensional patterns. Conversely, when pottery lacks particularly striking elements, individuals may form a holistic impression of the object or focus less attention overall. This may explain why, in such cases, the entire piece of pottery is selected as a region of interest.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE STUDIES

Jomon deep bowls were predominantly used for cooking purposes. However, the bold protrusions found in Okinohara and Umataka types, including flame-like pots, would have been impractical for inserting and removing food during cooking. This raises the possibility that these vessels were not primarily designed for culinary use, but rather as expressions of conceptual ideas influenced by the worldview of the Jomon people. Despite this, most bowls with exaggerated protrusions show clear evidence of use in cooking, bottom remains of charred foods.

Among ancient pottery worldwide, such exaggerated protrusions are uniquely characteristic of pottery from the middle Jomon period, particularly from the Shinano River basin, where flame-like pots are prominent. This distinct feature makes them notable even on a global scale [1].

a Conclusions-Sensory Impression Structure

The primary finding of this study is the significant prominence of "vigor" and "attractiveness" as key components in the sensory impression structure among participants who viewed holograms of four Umataka (flame-1 and 2, crown-1 and 2) pots and two Okinohara pots (Okinohara-1 and 2) using MR equipment. This result appears to be influenced by the remarkably expressive design, especially the four prominent protrusions characteristic of the pots.

In addition, this study contributes to advancing the understanding of the cognitive structure underlying sensory impressions of archaeological and cultural artifacts. It also underscores the potential of MR technology to enhance visitor engagement in museum settings.

b Challenges in Cognitive Studies Employing Deep Learning Models

The Active Inference and the Large Language Models are key issues advancing neuroscience and cognitive science [13][14].

In future studies, sensory impressions of participants who observe pottery and clay figurines will be used to train a deep learning model embedded with 3D-RGB data of the objects, within the framework of a Large Language Model (LLM). When new 3D-RGB data of objects are input into the trained model, it reproduces heatmaps and impression texts, which represent the "cognitive structure and body perception [5]."

Abstract thinking is considered one of the defining characteristics of modern humans, *Homo sapiens* (McBrearty and Brooks, 2000)[15]. The connection between object data and the abstract thinking of the mind—often referred to as the bridging point—is one of the most challenging aspects in advancing practical research. Future studies will focus on methods to extract psychological insights from vast amounts of object data. When contemporary individuals view holograms of Jomon pottery and clay figures, sensory impressions are assessed using the Semantic Differential Method (SDM), linguistic expressions are analyzed by large language models (LLMs), and visual perceptions are

recorded via gaze tracking and analyzed by 3D convolutional-deconvolutional models[16][17][18]. All cognitive and perceptual data are collected using a single mixed reality (MR) device. A deep learning model that simulates abstract thinking is employed to bridge the gap between multidimensional human perceptions, the cognitive structures of sensory impressions, verbal expressions, and physical objects. The integration of these multidimensional human senses, impressions, and expressions with deep learning models remains a central focus of future research.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DISCLOSURE

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interests relating to the content of this article.

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No.1 Okinohara-1 Okinohara, Coil Building

No.2 Okinohara-2 Okinohara, Coil Building

No.3 Umataka-flame1 Umataka (flame-like pot), Coil Building

No.4 Upper Ento Upper Ento, Coil Building

No.5 Umataka-flame2 Umataka (flame-like pot), Coil Building

No.6 Umataka-crown1 Umataka (crown-like pot), Coil Building

No.7 Umataka-crown2 Umataka (crown-like pot), Coil Building

No.8 Katsusaka Katsusaka, Coil Building

No.9 Sue ware Sue II-2, Wheel Forming

